

The Importance of Aikido Oriental Martial Arts in Training the Body and Spirit

Kambarov Nodirjon Sattarovich¹

¹ University of Business and Science Philosophy of pedagogical sciences doctor (PhD). Uzbekiston

Annotation:

In this article, opinions are expressed and the importance of training and education of the human body and soul through Aikido Eastern martial arts, factors, solutions is provided. The doctrines of Aikido Eastern martial arts will be discussed. Its main structural factors and parts are described. The criteria for the formation of a healthy lifestyle and the development of the population's interest in Eastern Aikido martial arts were analyzed and compared with the criteria. Recommendations were made for the removal of body and soul.

Keywords: Aikido Eastern martial arts, Body and soul, training, well-rounded person, recovery, biological body, astral body, healthy thinking, training, behavior, behavior, environment.

INTRODUCTION

Today, a lot of attention is paid to human health in the world. The importance of sports and martial arts is great in raising a person to be healthy, educated, capable and mature physically, spiritually, aesthetically and spiritually. The teachings of Eastern martial arts, especially the martial art of Aikido, are incomparable.

Aikido is one of the important tasks of training a well-rounded person, training the body and soul through this tool. The task of Aikido Eastern martial arts is solved positively if the martial arts practitioners understand the physical and technical-tactical methods in essence, or if they are interested in Eastern martial arts training and take the initiative to be creative, the correct formation of movement skills in the body, functional abilities they need to acquire technical-tactical, philosophical-pedagogical knowledge for their growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The article discusses the factors that help to educate a well-rounded person, train the body and soul, and develop a person healthy in all aspects through Aikido Eastern martial arts. Its main structural factors and parts are described. The criteria aimed at developing the interest of all strata of the population in Aikido Eastern martial arts, developing the human body and soul were analyzed and compared with the criteria. Aikido Eastern martial arts and approaches to psychology and physiology were studied.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND CONSIDERATIONS

Do not judge by appearance, the body is a sword and the soul is a sword.

Abu Raykhan Beruni

To research the possibilities of educating a person as a well-rounded person in the world, to study the impact of physical, mental, aesthetic, moral perfection on social activity, in particular, to develop new scientific and practical pedagogical models of the process of improving people's education as a well-rounded person innovative methods in their creation and implementation, application of technologies, a means of self-realization of the individual, attitude towards the traditions of Aikido Eastern martial arts, from the teachings of scholars, psychologists, martial arts masters and founders in the process of Aikido Eastern martial arts training scientific research is being carried out on education using it. The practical significance of Aikido Eastern martial arts is very important and relevant in helping young people to become fully mature individuals.

The acceleration and speed of the world development process complicates the upbringing of a mentally and physically healthy generation. In the age of great communication, the wide range of people's communication increases their moral and spiritual stress. Intolerance, nervousness, and depression are observed among members of society. In such a situation, the task of making the environment healthy in every society, raising the future generation mentally and physically healthy requires urgency. Taking into account the fact that human development takes place in a spiritual, physical, spiritual, moral-aesthetic harmony, tasks such as raising young people to be well-rounded individuals are being set. Therefore, in all countries, a number of reforms are being carried out in the systematic organization of raising a healthy generation in all respects.

Pedagogical scientist, founder of mental and physical knowledge P.F. Lesgaft "Mental and physical, spiritual and moral development are inextricably linked. The growth and development of the mind, in turn, leads to physical development" [159].

The task of Aikido Eastern martial arts is solved positively if martial arts practitioners perform physical and technical-tactical methods in essence, or if they are interested in Aikido Eastern martial arts training and take the initiative to be creative, the correct formation of movement skills in the body, functional they need to acquire. In this regard, L.P. Matveev expressed the following opinion: "Physical culture is a complex of achievements in the creation of special tools, forms, methods and conditions and their rational use for the purposeful realization of the physical development of members of society. Physical culture is a component of the general culture, its rise, the basis of the development of society" [1]. Therefore, physical culture consists of the result of creating conditions for a person's well-rounded personality education and their rational use. Technical-tactical, philosophical-pedagogical knowledge for the growth of their abilities.

Aikido is the main teaching of Eastern martial arts, it aims to be strong, strong-willed, physically and mentally healthy, beautiful at heart, patriotic, hard-working, honest, intellectually mature, hardworking, and a well-rounded person who always helps the weak. teaches philosophical observation. It is said that "A warrior should be strong like a mountain, dignified, burning like a fire, fast like a wind, quiet like a forest, and clear like the sky."

Aikido martial arts teachers not only train accomplished athletes and martial arts masters, but also

teach them to overcome life's difficulties. This guarantees that Aikido, as a comprehensive art form, will grow into a well-rounded person in the future. Even if, for some reason, they do not engage in these types of martial arts, the mental, physical, aesthetic and moral education instilled in these trainings is of great importance to young people in solving various problems throughout their lives.

It is appropriate and important to familiarize with the types and history, teachings of Eastern martial arts, and then engage in these martial arts. Martial arts are taught with a philosophical perspective. After all, let the learner become not only a warrior, but also a sound-thinking, well-rounded person.

Aikido Eastern martial arts is a way for a person throughout his life to physically train his body, strengthen his soul, develop aesthetic and moral education, and strive to open up new possibilities and abilities. To know this, it is necessary to deeply master the roots of Aikido Eastern martial arts.

Humans are given two bodies by the Creator. The first is the biological body and the second is the astral body.

The biological body is the physical body of a person. This includes bones, muscles, flesh, tendons, and blood.

The astral body is a rune. The soul cannot be grasped by human hands and cannot be seen by human eyes.

People and scientists have been debating whether the body is primary or the soul. In the teachings of Aikido martial arts, the idea that the soul is primary is put forward. Many people do not believe in the existence of a soul. In Eastern martial arts teachings and other religions, there are views about the existence of the soul and its unlimited possibilities.

In Eastern martial arts, the body and soul are likened to a sword in a scabbard.

The thinker Abu Raikhan Beruni said, "Do not judge by the body, the body is a dagger, and the soul is a sword." In this way, he likens the soul to a sword in a scabbard.

Or Aikido fighters teach you to use your sword when you fight. Aikido master Yasinaru Kitara said, "My soul is what connects heaven and earth."

The main purpose of Aikido martial arts is to train the body and soul. Aikido, in its essence, is a harmonious way of the soul.

Aikido martial arts. Aikido, another form of Japanese oriental martial arts, was founded by Morihei Uyeshiba in the early 20th century. Uyeshiba's martial art of Aikido is now studied in all countries and promoted by aikido masters who learned directly from its founders. All aikido practitioners consider Uyeshiba to be their great teacher, master (OSENSEI).

Master (OSENSEI) Morihei Uyeshiba was born on December 14, 1883 in Tanabe, Japan, and he is a representative of the old and last generation of samurai.

Aikido, which appeared in eastern Japan, was taught only to a narrow circle of people for many years. Aikido martial art has become a more precise and perfect martial art among the eastern martial arts, able to unite all physical, aesthetic, moral, and spiritual powers of a person and effectively use it. Aikido is a way of harmony (existence) of "Ai", "Ki" of spiritual power, inner strength, body and soul. The short meaning of the word "Aikido" means "The harmonious way of the soul". The originality of this martial art, founded by Uyeshiba, includes Japanese swordsmanship (kendo), javelin (judo), ji-jitsu and many other relatively ancient specific thoughts, actions, and the same Esoteric type of martial art based on "ki" spiritual energy, "do" means path, style, which is the basis of a specific martial art [3]. The martial art of Aikido is an effective self-defense style, sometimes with surprising results, that can be used against attacks from one or more opponents, making it suitable for people of all ages. and means that people of the gender can

engage. Aikido martial arts movements are usually performed in a spherical direction. Aikido competitions are strictly prohibited. This is due to the fact that he had a deep moral education, such as throwing using the opponent's strength, twisting his hands, and holding him in pain. If competitions are held, athletes can get many injuries. Therefore, only seminars and festivals are held on Aikido. But in Aikido, there are no methods of hitting a person. An aikido player uses the strength of an opponent and defeats him without causing physical injury.

The health aspect of Aikido. Practice of Aikido is carried out at different levels, because the final result is the perfect education of the human personality, the integration of physical and mental, and at the same time functional forces. First of all, it should be noted that the practice of Aikido is characterized by specific circular movements and the use of clear, flat physical and mental strength. Even women, children and elderly people have a feature that regulates the coordination of mental and physical activity. The clear result of regular Aikido practice is the improvement of health, especially in the respiratory and circulatory systems. If the respiratory system is improved by proper abdominal breathing, the blood circulation system ensures the normal functioning of the joints and the body as a whole. As a result, the breathing and blood circulation system improves, it gives the blood the opportunity to quickly and constantly deliver new nutrients to all organs. In the martial art of Aikido, a person learns to receive, concentrate and apply his own energy and energy from the outside world. In this, the body is also trained through mental energy. Great results are achieved through the harmony of body and soul. Through this, a strong aura is created in a person. The science of aura is a psychological and physiological process, a person develops it by constantly performing various exercises. A strong aura creates a healthy and strong temperament.

Aikido martial arts training is an excellent pedagogical process in which the role of the teacher and student is important. "If you want to find a good teacher, be sincere!" [3] - it is said in Aikido martial arts.

Therefore, the following positive relationship has been established between the student (pupil) and the teacher (mentor):

1. The teacher always calls his student to the path of truth. Therefore, it easily prompts the reader and eliminates his mistakes. It provides theoretical and practical help in saving time and energy.
2. The technical and spiritual content of Aikido cannot be expressed in words alone. The key here is intuition. In training, more "body language" is used. The teacher himself shows the methods with the help of actions. That is why work is carried out on each type of movement. It will be necessary to strictly follow this in training.
3. With the help of the teacher, the student develops confidence, courage and determination. Young people feel the responsibility to consolidate what they have learned from their teacher and pass it on to their students in the future. As a result, Aikido martial arts has taken an important place in the life of young people, it is a real and constantly renewing force.

Pedagogical teachings of Eastern martial arts embody the art of the heart and the path of truth. The purpose of the art of the heart is to summarize the personal experiences of the inner and outer world of young people in an aesthetic creation. Art is manifested in the psychological understanding of inner experiences and the interaction of faith and abstraction.

Aikido differs from other martial arts in that it can be practiced not only by young people, but also by adults and people of various professions.

From the above points, it can be seen that as many nations as there are on earth, all of them have their own national martial arts. These are the martial arts that are unique to that nation, originated from its customs, climate, mentality, and needs, and have been preserved until now. Some of them are spread around the world and popular, some are hidden and inherited only by their own families.

They protected their family and country through martial arts. First of all, they tried to be healthy. These martial arts, which have trained the body and soul and have reached our times, have turned into sports in which competitions are held not only for protection and health, but also to raise the mood of people and interest them in this martial arts. Many people are currently engaged in oriental martial arts. They use it to form a healthy lifestyle and introduce their country to the world.

XULOSALAR

In conclusion, there is a need to educate young people on the basis of a new approach to physical, mental, moral, spiritual education, strengthening of health, and promotion of a healthy lifestyle through Aikido Eastern martial arts, in order to help young people to become well-rounded individuals in all aspects. is happening Perfect personality education, like other forms of education, is a part of the system that develops a person comprehensively. To teach children and teenagers to take care of their health, to create a healthy lifestyle in them by practicing Aikido martial arts The highest goal of the pedagogical process is to improve the skills of continuous, independent engagement with Aikido martial arts.

REFERENCES:

1. Matveev L.P. Vsestoronnaya physicheskaya podgotovka kak uslovie sportivnoy spetsializatsii: Autoreferat, dis. - Mokva, 2019. P. 47.
2. Abdullaev A, Honkeldiev Sh.Kh. Theory and methodology of physical education. - T.: UzDJTI publishing house. 2005. – P 5, 23, 54, 63.
3. Brand R. Aikido. - Moscow, 2003. P. 11,12,26.
4. Avloni A. Turkish culture or ethics. - Tashkent. P. 11.